

**SOCIAL, LEGAL, ECONOMIC, SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL
DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY AND DEMOCRATIC STATE**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6646561>

Social development in the world, democratic reforms, the priority tasks associated with the construction of civil society, the importance of the idea of national independence, as an object of national prestige and social protection in international relations, show how important it is in the life of society.

The practice of developing new innovations in the formation of a global ideological world in the minds of different strata of the population in a number of institutions and scientific research centers of the world on the issues of restoration of a strong managerial power in the implementation of democratic reforms, ideological justification of the political system is rapidly developing.

The development strategy of the new Uzbekistan is recognized by the international community as one of the countries achieving ideological stability. The national ideological system became the ideological basis of state and public organizations. The main reason for this is a highly developed, ultimate goal, an indicator of creating a free and prosperous life for our people". The work to be done in this regard hitherto miser.

The impact of ideological upbringing, which serves to form a broad, spiritually harmonious person of the worldview, is felt to be reduced. It is inevitable that the National idea, which is the prospect of the new Uzbekistan dream, will become the spirit of creativity of societies that have reached the advanced level of development, the idea of a highly developed person and nation.

Decree of the president of the Republic of Azerbaijan on measures to ensure more effective organization of the process of acquisition of rights over land parcels and other immovable property as part of the South Caucasus pipeline expansion project more ... and in the circle of development of the educational system ", Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures to ensure more effective organization of the process of acquisition of rights over land parcels and other immovable property as part of the South Caucasus pipeline expansion project more ...

This dissertation is devoted to the development of Science and technology of the Republic. The priority direction" formation and implementation of the system of innovative ideas in the social, legal, economic, spiritual and educational development of an informed society and a Democratic state " has been successfully implemented.

Level of study of the problem. President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Mirziyoyev's new strategy of Uzbekistan and its "people's State", "Fair social policy", "spiritual development", "security and foreign policy", "Uzbekistan and universal problems" concerted ideas on the performance of such important tasks served as a scientific and methodological basis for this research.

In the rich ideological framework of Eastern thinkers, the doctrine of the National idea, including social views, which are important for the family, the purity and morality of society, is described in Avesto, and the special aspect of human beings that distinguishes them from animals, and the space that preserves the purity and purity of generation, as well as the fact that they are family,

Also, the life, activities, ideas of justice, the prospects of the National idea, the members of the society and the public administration are fully compatible with such thinkers as Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Mansur Motrudiy, Abu Rayhon Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, who are the founders of ideological awakening. In the booklet "about statehood and baht Iqbal" of AR Roziy, issues of educational literacy of Turkic peoples in the work "Devonu loğotit turk" of Mahmud Qashgari, teacher of the jadid school S. In the work of sayidmurodzadeh Ayny "slaves", the idea of the nation is manifested as a unifying and comforting power in the work of ideological barbarism and ways to get rid of it, The Great Sahibqiran Amir Temur "Temur regiments".

In the teachings of Western thinkers, in particular F. Bacon claims that it is necessary to be a creator of life, such as a honey bee, not to collect everything that grows on a human ant, but to wrap it in its shell, like a spider, Decart brings to science the function of "reasonable doubt" in relation to destructive ideas that oppose creative ideas, as an ideological basis. At the beginning of the XVIII century, the views of the French thinker Walter in his work "universal experiments on the spirituality and Ruhi of the people" about the fact that the idea of a nation should be in harmony with the idea of the world, are recognized as an ideology against communist ideas. He is an American scientist in the XX century. James argues that by creating the "American spirit", popular ideas must have an integration of religious, philosophical and scientific aspects.

Scientists from the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), in particular, Russian scientists V.M. Petrova-national ideological issues of the Russian state, T. Zikova, T. Shadrina-the code of success of the Russian national idea, V.G. Fedotova said that values in Russia and the West are subject to change, and

their Goyas are based, V.V.Sogrin-characteristic features of Goya Uzi in American history, L.Ionin national psychology of Goya intolerance, scientists of Tatarstan M.I.Ibragimov, A.I.Suit jacket – Tatarstan national identity idea, T.G.Okriashvili-those who carried out scientific research on such topics as the theoretical basis of the tatar national idea.

Scientific theoretical research of national ideological importance in the countries of Central Asia, Kyrgyz scientist K.K.Imanaliev-national-ideological and ethnocultural development of the Kyrgyz state, Khalik A.- A new occupation of the development of a national idea in Tajikistan, A.S.Janosinova-Kozakstan conducted scientific research on the analysis of the national strategy.

Philosophical scientific views on the study of the historical significance of the National idea in Uzbekistan, its ideological basis, its role in ensuring political, social and economic stability.Tyulenov, S.It was formed in the works of Uzbek scientists such as shermukhammedov. A.Erkaev, J.Goodness, Q.Kuranbaev said that the National idea was the nation's optimistic namely life-giving idea, N.Shermukhamedova revealed that ideological maturity is manifested in the harmony of social activity and social responsibility. X.Zieev, Sh.Qakhkharova, E.Yusupov and others conducted research on the spiritual and ideological basis of human perfection.

USED LITERATURE:

1. Sh.Mirziyoyev's answers to the questions of the editor-in-chief of the new Uzbekistan newspaper. 18 August, 2021 year.
2. Sh.Mirziyaev. New Uzbekistan strategy.Tashkent."Uzbekistan", 2021.P.272.
3. Sh.Mirziyaev. New Uzbekistan strategy.Tashkent."Uzbekistan", 2021.- Page 9
4. The same work.- Page 16.